

Generation of virtual patient data for *in-silico* cardiomyopathies drug development using tree ensembles: a comparative study

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Abstract—*In-silico* clinical platforms have been recently used as a new revolutionary path for virtual patients (VP) generation and further analysis, such as, drug development. Advanced individualized models have been developed to enhance flexibility and reliability of the virtual patient cohorts. This study focuses on the implementation and comparison of three different methodologies for generating virtual data for *in-silico* clinical trials. Towards this direction, three computational methods, namely: (i) the multivariate log-normal distribution (log-MVND), (ii) the supervised tree ensembles, and (iii) the unsupervised tree ensembles are deployed and evaluated against their performance towards the generation of high-quality virtual data using the goodness of fit (gof) and the dataset correlation matrix as performance evaluation measures. Our results reveal the dominance of the tree ensembles towards the generation of virtual data with similar distributions (avg. gof values less than 0.2) and correlation patterns (avg. difference less than 0.03).

Keywords: virtual population generation, cardiomyopathy, *in-silico* clinical trials, log-MVND, tree ensembles.

I. INTRODUCTION

Virtual population (VP) development is a very popular and emerging aspect of healthcare technology, where the recent computational advances have shed light into the impact of this rapidly evolving biomedical field. According to the literature, many studies refer to VPs and present them as simulated 3D visualizations of human patients, which could be potentially used to train clinicians. On the other hand, other studies refer to geometrical models of VPs, which are reconstructed from the virtual data to extract valuable clinical information. Their purpose is to create large atlas datasets to represent big varied cohorts depending on the disease under investigation.

Hence, in this study, we refer to those mathematical models whose generation is based on algorithms. Mathematical models are often used to describe and predict the patient's progression according to an existing therapy. Such models try to simulate clinical trials for numerous applications of drug development and support decision making in clinical trials and constitute the clinical trial simulations (CTS). The knowledge mining from these models leads to the reduction,

refinement and partial substitution of the animal and human experimentation for drug development. The definition of CTS presupposes the reliable reproduction of the clinical trial design, the drug efficacy and the disease progression. A difficult issue of this field is the quality of the provided data. Towards this direction, data curation methods can be used to resolve any errors that are present within the data (e.g., outliers, inconsistencies) and thus yield high quality data for much more accurate virtual population generation.

The major baseline approaches for VPs generation can be grouped in two categories, parametric and non-parametric [1]. The multivariate normal distribution (MVND) method used first studied and implemented by Tanenbaum [1] to generate a target group of virtual patients based on realistic covariates. Teutonico et al. [2] evaluated and compared the MVND approach with resampling. Their results optimized MVND as it could provide new patients across different ranges of values. Furthermore, some other studies that used different techniques are worth to be mentioned due to their increased performance. Regnier et al. [3] implemented and evaluated three different approaches to generate VPs that would match the real distributions from clinical cohorts. Moreover, Allen et al. [4], introduced a novel technique to generate VPs and demonstrated an efficient approach to select VP that matches the observed data without the need for weighting. Apart from the conventional multivariate methods, more straightforward methods, such as, the tree ensembles have been recently proposed by Robnik-Šikonja [5] for the generation of robust semiartificial data, however, without any reported application for *in-silico* clinical trials.

In this work, we deploy three computational methods to generate virtual patient data from real clinical data. We extend a previous study [6], where the MVND method was used to generate 300 virtual patients by comparing the multivariate log-normal distribution with the tree ensembles to generate 1000 virtual patients for *in-silico* clinical trials targeting the drug development for familiar cardiomyopathies (FCM). These methods have been integrated into the *in-silico* clinical trial SILICOFCM cloud-based platform [7]. The latter

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incorporates straightforward simulation tools for FCM drug development. Our results confirm the dominance of the tree ensembles as a prominent method for virtual population generation yielding an increased level of agreement between the real and the virtual data with average gof values less than 0.2 and correlation patterns similar to the real data (2.71% difference in the average correlation values).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

B. Data sharing

Anonymized data were obtained from 1227 patients at two timepoints (2454 records in total) under the SILICOFM project [7]. The dataset included 29 features (17 discrete, 12 continuous) related to demographic (e.g., age, gender), laboratory measures (e.g., diastolic pressure), and gene-related information (e.g., ACTC1, CSRP3). All the data came from the same centre, the Cardiomyopathies Unit at Careggi Hospital, Florence, and were collected by a very limited number of clinicians over more than 20 years.

B. Data quality evaluation

A data quality control pipeline presented in a previous study [8,9] was applied on the clinical data to deal with outliers, incompatible fields, duplicated features and missing values, where the Interquartile range (IQR) method was used to detect outliers and the Jaro distance [10] for lexical similarities. Features with more than 50% missing values, outliers, inconsistent fields were ignored from the analysis.

C. Methods for generating virtual data

1) Multivariate log-normal distribution

The multivariate normal distribution (MVND) [1,2] was adopted as a standard approach towards the generation of virtual patient data. Assuming a set of p –features, say $\mathbf{x} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_p\}$, the MVND is defined as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{p/2} |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu})\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}-\boldsymbol{\mu})}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the dimension, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the mean vector, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is the covariance matrix, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}$ is the pseudoinverse of the covariance matrix which is estimated through singular value decomposition (SVD). The goal of the MVND is to construct a multi-dimensional normal distribution given the mean vector, $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and the covariance matrix, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$. In an attempt to strengthen the assumption of the normal distribution among the real data, we generated samples that follow a log-normal distribution, where the exponential of (1) was used to generate virtual data so that:

$$\ln(\mathbf{e}^{f(\mathbf{x})}) \sim N(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}), \quad (2)$$

The generated values from $\mathbf{e}^{f(\mathbf{x})}$ were finally log-normally transformed and compared with the original ones.

2) Supervised tree ensembles

Another straightforward approach for virtual population generation is to train tree ensembles [11] given a set of training features along with a target feature. The virtual population generation problem can then be seen as a supervised learning problem, where the tree ensembles are

trained on an annotated subset and tested on the remaining subset. The classifier can then be turned into a virtual data generator to generate semi-artificial data that follow the same distribution as the original data [11]. During the training process, the Gini impurity index [12] is used to measure the probability of a variable being classified in the wrong class as follows:

$$I(p) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i^2, \quad (3)$$

where p_i is the probability of a sample falling in class $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, where k is the total number of classes ($k = 2$ for a binary target feature). The Semiartificial package in R [11] was used to create a tree ensemble.

3) “Unsupervised” tree ensembles

A similar and rather straightforward approach for virtual population generation is to see the virtual population as a regression problem using tree ensembles [11]. The regressor can then be turned into a virtual data generator to generate semi-artificial data that follow the same distribution as the original data [11]. During the training process, the Mean Square Error (MSE) [11] is used to measure the difference between the real and the virtual distributions. For two variables (features), assume \mathbf{x}_r and \mathbf{x}_v , in the real and virtual distributions, respectively, the MSE is given as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_{r,i} - x_{v,i})^2, \quad (4)$$

The Semiartificial package in R [11] was used to construct a tree ensemble which was used as virtual generator.

D. Evaluation measures

1) Goodness of fit

The Kolmogorov-Smirnoff goodness of fit (gof) statistical test [13] was used to measure the level of agreement between the real and the virtual distributions. The gof test measures whether the virtual data instances and the real data instances come from the same distribution. More specifically, the gof test statistics, say g , is given as:

$$g = \max(|f_r(\mathbf{x}) - f_v(\mathbf{x})|), \quad (5)$$

where $f_r(\mathbf{x})$ and $f_v(\mathbf{x})$ are the empirical distribution functions of the original and virtual data, respectively. Large g values denote distributions with large vertical distance between them, whereas small g values denote distribution with small vertical distances.

2) Correlation

To further evaluate the similarity of the real and virtual data we computed the Pearson’s correlation coefficient between each pair of features in the virtual data and the real data. For two variables (features), assume \mathbf{x}_r and \mathbf{x}_v , in the real and virtual distributions, respectively, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient [14], assume r , is given as:

$$r = \frac{E[(\mathbf{x}_r - \mu_{x_r})(\mathbf{y}_r - \mu_{y_r})]}{\sigma_{x_r} \sigma_{y_r}}, \quad (6)$$

where μ_{x_r} , μ_{y_r} are the mean values and σ_{x_r} , σ_{y_r} are the standard deviations of \mathbf{x}_r and \mathbf{y}_r , respectively, and $E[.]$ is the

expected value. An r value 1 denotes a perfect positive correlation between x_r and y_r , whereas an r value of 0 denotes no correlation.

III. RESULTS

A. Data quality assessment

The total number of missing values within the data was 10.12% (13 features had less than 50% missing values and 16 features had no missing values at all). Neither outliers nor duplicated features or inconsistent fields were detected in the anonymized data.

B. Virtual population generation

The clinical experts examined the resulting curated dataset and selected a subset of 10 features for generating 1000 virtual patients. The subset of features consists of the following features: “LVOTO_Rest” (Left ventricular outflow tract obstruction during resting state) (mean = 19.79, std = 21.79), “Evel” (E wave velocity) (mean = 74.8, std = 22.46), “lat_Eprime” (lateral e’ wave) (mean = 9.8, std = 3.02), “sep_Eprime” (septal e’ wave) (mean = 6.86, std = 2.14), “LA” (Left Atrium) (mean = 44.23, std = 7.39), “LVEF” (Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction) (mean = 64.25, std = 8.6), “Max_LVT” (maximum Left Ventricular Thickness) (mean = 19.24, std = 5.88), “PW” (mean = 10.68, std = 2.08), “NYHA” (New York Heart Association class) (mean = 1.65, std = 0.71) and “Age” (mean = 51.33, std = 18.19).

The performance evaluation results for each type of virtual population generation method are presented in Table 1, where the gof values where the smallest for the features “Max_LVT” and “Age” in the log-MVND, for the features “sep_Eprime”, “LA”, “PW”, and “Age” in the supervised tree ensembles and for the remaining features in the unsupervised tree ensembles.

TABLE 1: PERFORMANCE EVALUATION RESULTS FOR EACH TYPE OF VIRTUAL POPULATION GENERATION METHOD.

Feature	Performance evaluation measures		
	mean	std	gof*
Multivariate log-normal distribution			
LVOTO_Rest	22.93	16.76	0.28
Evel	75.10	22.36	0.18
lat_Eprime	9.79	3.04	0.25
sep_Eprime	6.89	2.09	0.24
LA	43.89	7.30	0.10
LVEF	64.08	8.69	0.18
Max_LVT	19.08	6.00	0.10
PW	10.51	1.99	0.19
NYHA	1.63	0.76	0.27
Age	51.49	18.36	0.04
Supervised tree ensembles			
LVOTO_Rest	18.67	24.50	0.20
Evel	78.54	34.06	0.16
lat_Eprime	9.38	3.56	0.23
sep_Eprime	6.64	2.59	0.18
LA	43.60	7.26	0.09
LVEF	65.25	6.09	0.14
Max_LVT	17.60	5.00	0.14
PW	10.48	2.25	0.16
NYHA	1.53	0.68	0.09
Age	52.30	17.55	0.04
Unsupervised tree ensembles			
LVOTO_Rest	19.85	26.52	0.19
Evel	78.25	31.71	0.15

lat_Eprime	9.63	3.64	0.19
sep_Eprime	6.56	2.74	0.24
LA	42.97	7.26	0.14
LVEF	64.28	7.54	0.07
Max_LVT	17.70	4.73	0.13
PW	10.39	2.03	0.17
NYHA	1.51	0.62	0.07
Age	52.03	17.59	0.06

*The smallest gof values on each method are filled with gray color.

The distribution of the gof values for each type of virtual population generation method is depicted in Figure 1 for the set of features which is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Distribution plots for the real (upper panel; blue color) and the virtual data (lower panel; light blue: log-MVND, green: supervised tree ensembles, orange: unsupervised tree ensembles).

The correlation matrix of the real data is depicted in Figure 3 whereas the correlation matrix for the virtual data that were derived by the unsupervised tree ensembles (as the method that achieved the highest number of “optimal” gof values) is depicted in Figure 3, showing similar association patterns within the data. High correlation values are depicted in deep blue color whereas low correlation values are depicted in yellow. Since this is a qualitative way to view the correlation between the features in the real and the virtual populations, we have also computed the absolute value of the difference between the average correlation values from the upper (or lower) triangular part of the matrices, for quantitative purposes. The difference in the average correlation values was

4.45% for the log-MVND, 8.28% for the supervised tree ensembles and 2.71% for the unsupervised tree ensembles.

Figure 2: Correlation matrix of the real data.

Figure 3: Correlation matrix of the virtual data that were generated by the "unsupervised" tree ensembles.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we compared three computational methods towards the generation of 1000 high-quality, virtual patient data for *in silico* clinical trials in cardiomyopathies drug development using the goodness of fit (gof) and the correlation matrix for performance evaluation purposes. Our results suggest the dominance of the tree ensembles for virtual population generation yielding virtual patient data with an increased level of agreement (distributions with less than 0.2 gof) and at the same time maintaining the correlation patterns (associations) among the features in the real clinical data.

More specifically, the "unsupervised" tree ensembles achieved the lowest goodness-of-fit values for five out of ten features according to Table 1 and Figure 1 (i.e., for the clinical features "LVOTO_Rest", "Evel", "lat_Eprime", "LVEF", and "NYHA"), the supervised tree ensembles for four out of ten features (i.e., the "sep_Eprime", "LA", "PW", and "Age") using "NYHA" as the target feature and finally the log-MVND for only two out of ten features (i.e., the "Max_LVT", and "Age"). The correlation matrix that was generated by the "unsupervised" tree ensembles was close to the original one,

a fact that enhances the level of agreement between the virtual and the real data. For example, the strong association between the lateral e' wave ("latEprime") and the septal e' wave ("sepEprime") (Figure 2) which is high (more than 75%) is clearly preserved in the virtual population (Figure 3).

The proposed methods could potentially provide significant insight in the field of virtual population generation to re-adjust the perspective of Clinical Trials (CTs) in other domains. As a future work, we also plan to deploy artificial neural networks (ANNs) that make use of radial basis functions (RBFs) as activation functions towards the generation of even more robust clinical data for *in-silico* clinical trials.

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